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DEVELOPMENT OF A NEXT-GENERATION CORPORATE SERVICE PLATFORM

PRODUCT PRESENTATION BROCHURE

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1. INTRODUCTION

Mobilegap Magyarország Zrt. was established to fill a general professional gap in specific engineering fields, particularly in the telecommunications sector and among suppliers. Our continuously expanding team possesses extensive expertise and preparedness, now offering comprehensive solutions in multi-supplier environments across all branches of telecommunications and IT sectors.

In response to market demands and opportunities, Mobilegap Magyarország Zrt. has expanded beyond its existing competencies and opened up to new opportunities.

Thanks to our expertise and experience in telecommunications, we can contribute to defining network development directions, as well as testing network and business solutions. To achieve our research and development goals, we utilize commercially available measuring instruments and design software alongside our own proprietary support platforms, developed exclusively through our internal R&D programs and engineers' expertise. In addition to our system integration activities, we also support and operate the networks and complex systems we deploy.

Under the Economic Development and Innovation Operational Program, the company received funding for the project titled "Development of a Next-Generation Corporate Service Platform" with the identification number GINOP-2.1.2-8-1-4-16-2017-00240, under the call for proposals "Supporting Corporate R&D&I Activities." The total project value was HUF 231,381,140, out of which HUF 115,687,392 was granted in support. The project was implemented between March 1, 2019, and May 29, 2021.

2. RESEARCH PROJECT CONTENT

The project involved the creation of a platform extending from the client endpoint through the communication network to the control of applications in the central cloud. The goal of the platform is to automate and centrally manage the resources used by various services, including endpoints, network connections, and cloud computing, networking, and storage.

The framework developed through the project provides several technological innovations. The core of the service is an application running on a cloud-based platform, and its main innovation compared to existing market solutions is its multi-purpose usability. The final system is applicable in various domains with significantly reduced resource expenditure.

A key example of the platform's functionality is the integration of IoT devices, processing data from these devices, storing it in a database, and displaying it in an interface. This feature can serve as a foundation for SME services, such as smart devices and customized IoT solutions.

The platform's resource management functions facilitate the execution of applications.

The project also involved the development of a customer relationship and service development portal, enabling the integration, testing, and enhancement of the entire service chain. The system was also tested in a laboratory environment to validate its efficiency.

The platform itself serves as the core product, allowing clients to dynamically build service packages based on their needs. Example applications include:

- Cloud-based smart security solutions (office and site protection, smart office)
- Centralized, cloud-controlled office applications
- Sales and manufacturing systems

Our goal is to align IT system development needs with corporate strategies, ensuring that services introduced to the market support enterprise-wide digital transformation.

Beyond service development, we plan to introduce comprehensive support services covering the full lifecycle from product development to operations. Key features include:

- Plug-and-play solutions customized for different business sizes and profiles
- Cloud-based services, M2M communication, IoT
- Rapid deployment of custom solutions, including marketing automation
- Optimized resource utilization and impact analysis
- Lifecycle tracking and operational support
- Open-source development foundations

Currently, ICT services on the market are typically proprietary solutions that create vendor lock-in, making it difficult for clients to integrate custom functionalities dynamically. The open-source nature of the developed framework provides benefits such as:

- Enhanced security
- Community contributions
- Easier customization
- Optimized cost structure

The project's framework also incorporates cloud and software-defined network-based services, automating installation, scaling, resource allocation, and availability management. Furthermore, the developer portal enables the integration of IoT elements and management of complex rule-based automation.

The project also focused on edge computing, bringing applications and data processing closer to end users. A crucial component of the system is the IoT or CPE device installed at the client's premises, which is designed to minimize costs while maintaining high security and efficiency. Key innovations include:

- Minimal local functionality, with only essential operations running on the device
- Support for both IPv4 and IPv6, ensuring future-proof compatibility
- Simple software architecture, allowing for remote programmability
- Optional edge computing capabilities, enabling decentralized processing

The platform also facilitates the migration of traditional complex applications to a cloud-based model, reducing reliance on on-premise hardware while improving scalability and flexibility.

Automation is a key feature of the developed system, ensuring end-to-end dynamic provisioning. Without full automation, manual intervention at any level would limit the system's ability to function as a real-time, agile solution. The platform achieves this by providing a programmable, open interface for seamless integration and control.

3. KEY TECHNOLOGICAL COMPONENTS

The main components of the implemented platform are as follows:

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In our current research, we have developed a platform that supports IoT device connectivity, data collection and processing from these devices, as well as IoT development, system design, and future operations.

The core of the system is a cloud-based infrastructure service, which underpins the IoT developer platform software layer. The system is designed to function in a distributed manner, incorporating computing units that can operate independently of the central system. This offers several advantages, including offloading central infrastructure by processing large amounts of IoT data locally, thus reducing the volume of transmitted messages and network load. To achieve this decentralized model, we developed an infrastructure allowing individual nodes to function autonomously and execute stored logic.

Additionally, the platform is designed with modularity, making it easily adaptable to client needs. Thanks to its container-based architecture, the system is highly portable, quickly deployable, flexibly scalable, and easily manageable.

The system can be used efficiently across various fields, from ICT services for SMEs to healthcare, agriculture, and even consumer applications like IoT, IPTV, and home Wi-Fi routers. The platform also includes an IoT developer package, forming the foundation for IoT services for SMEs. It provides hardware and software resource management, supporting IoT-centric business applications and encouraging data-driven application development over traditional static models.

The system also integrates an IoT developer platform package, forming the foundation for IoT services for SMEs. The platform ensures access to the necessary hardware and software resources, enabling clients to manage computing, storage, and network resources efficiently. Furthermore, the IoT PaaS developer application built on this infrastructure supports the implementation of IoT-driven business applications, encouraging further adoption of the platform over traditional master data-based business applications.

4. ACHIEVED RESULTS

As a result of this research project, we successfully developed a system that enables:

- IoT-based smart building control and infotainment systems, integrating both installed and third-party functions into an interactive application/web interface.
- Application-level management of sports and tourism events, supporting e-mobility and dynamic service management using mobile communication networks.
- Adaptation to evolving business demands and expectations.
- The growing presence of cloud-based services.
- Application across enterprise, SME, and consumer segments.
- Development of interconnected 'SMART' systems, replacing traditional ICT platforms.
- Integration of sensor-based and self-learning solutions, customized to user environments and needs.
- Connection, data collection, and processing of IoT (Internet of Things) devices.
- A development and system design support platform for IoT applications, responding to client demands.

Beyond the initial implementation, the developed platform can be further enhanced based on operational experiences and evolving business needs. The knowledge and insights gained during the project open up possibilities for developing new market-ready products and establishing new services.

5 OPPORTUNITIES AND APPLICATION AREAS

Based on our experience so far, the developed process can be applied in the following areas in the future:

- Smart Reception
- Smart Car Care
- Smart Office
- Smart Information Systems

Additional advantages of our developed platform system include:

- Flexible scalability and development
- Modern technological solutions
- Customizable for clients and users

Several potential applications for the developed process have already emerged during the development phase.

The development of the platform and its related applications is broad and complex. Currently, we do not limit the service and application areas by precisely defining the target groups. However, in terms of final utilization, we can distinguish between primary and secondary target groups:

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- **Primary target group:** Domestic companies that provide ICT services to their customers. These are typically telecommunications companies, which will be the buyers and users of the project-developed framework. This group generally includes medium and large enterprises, seeking to expand into new market segments, such as Hungarian SMEs. The project's proposed solution creates new market opportunities while enabling efficient operations.
- **Secondary target group:** Domestic ICT service developers, who are looking for solutions to reduce market entry, business development, customer management, and operational burdens. They also seek to minimize service development costs. The project's proposed framework and business model address both concerns, allowing these companies to reach customers through cooperation with primary target group companies at significantly lower investment costs. Additionally, the platform offers substantial savings on development expenses.